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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF PATIENTS' SATISFACTION AND
ATTITUDE AFTER AND BEFORE COMPLETE DENTURES**Dr Tehlil¹, Dr Shahid Masood², Dr Abdul Haq³¹ Allied Hospital, Faisalabad² Lahore Medical and Dental College³ Ex House Officer, Pakistan Institute of Medical Science, PIMS Islamabad

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Abstract:

Aim: The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between patients' attitudes to obtaining a prosthesis and their satisfaction with a complete denture.

Place and Duration: In the Dental Section of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: 450 new total denture users took part in the study. In any case, the patient's attitude before performing the prosthesis was assessed using a questionnaire containing 12 questions in the "yes-no" model. Patient satisfaction with new teeth was assessed using a questionnaire consisting of 12 questions using an analog scale from 1 to 5 (1: I strongly disagree, 5: I strongly agree). The satisfaction test was carried out 3 months after implantation. Multiple correspondence analysis has shown a close relationship between the expectations of the patient's future prosthesis and the recognition of her new dentures after three months of use.

Results and Conclusion: Most people wearing a full denture were greatly satisfied and expressed overall satisfaction with convenience, maintenance, stability, speech, chewing, taste, appearance and no pain when wearing the denture. He accepted the method of treatment. They also stated that they would recommend similar treatment to others if needed.

Keywords: full denture, patient satisfaction, prosthetic dentistry, dental success.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Tehlil,

Allied Hospital, Faisalabad

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Becoming edentulous is an unpleasant phenomenon in the patient's life, and complete dentures can be a big disappointment for many patients without teeth¹⁻². Dentists believe that dentures are effective when they meet certain technological standards, but the patient assesses the dentures for their satisfaction. The biggest challenge when using dentures is the effective management of complete dentures for patients who have difficulty with their dentures. Usually, the patient's expectations and attitudes, not the patient's prosthetic or psychological technique, can lead to therapeutic failure³⁻⁴. Although the patient's attitude towards the prosthesis has proved to be an important factor when taking a full denture, many dentists have unrealistic expectations as to the functional and aesthetic value of the prosthesis. Bell noted that dentists should train their patients to have a realistic view of limiting the use of prostheses⁵⁻⁶. Numerous studies report the relationship between the professionally assessed and accepted quality of a complete denture and the subjective judgment of patients, among them many authors show interest in the right approach to the prosthesis, very few people who have studied this relationship with satisfaction, however, Van Waas found a moderate relationship between denture satisfaction and her approach to this prosthesis⁷⁻⁸. Jonkman et al reported that the approach to wearing a prosthesis was a potential tool for assessing the prosthesis when the attitude is positive and the patient expects a positive result; patients will be more satisfied with their prosthesis.

METHOD:

This study was held in the Dental Section of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. 450 patients participated in the study. The study population consisted of 230 men and 220 women aged 32-81. The average age was 51.3 years. To take part in the study, patients had to answer two series of questionnaires after the purpose of the study was explained to them at two different times (before treatment and three months after using a full denture). In addition, only typical patients were selected. Patients with physical and / or mental disabilities are not included in this study.

The questionnaire developed is based on questions from previous comparable studies. Selected questions were easy. Before starting this process, dentists working in a prosthetic clinic (two residents and a senior specialist) witnessed reading the problem to 20 patients to see if the results were consistent enough; it was then decided that only the lead specialist should make all records of all patients. Prostheses were made for patients with conventional methods of making dentures. The patient's attitude or expectations regarding prostheses were assessed using a questionnaire. Efforts were made to collect this data before starting

treatment. The survey begins to gather information on socioeconomic variables such as age, gender, occupation and marital status. The attitude towards the prostheses was measured using a questionnaire consisting of 12 questions: the first two try to explain the general expectations of the patient in terms of satisfaction and their thoughts on the comfort that they can feel in the prosthesis; seven questions about functional performance and aesthetic aspects; in the last three attempts were made to examine some psychological results during treatment, the questions were answered yes / no.

Three months after the new prosthesis was put in, patients' satisfaction with the new prostheses was generally measured using a questionnaire consisting of 12 questions. The first two questions were asked to express whether they were comfortable in the denture. The next seven questions are about the functional aspects of dentures: maintenance, stability, speech, chewing, taste, pain and appearance in dentures. The last three questions provided an assessment of the psychological aspects of dentures in terms of acceptance of dentures as part of themselves, the effectiveness of social relations with dentures, and whether they recommend this type of treatment to others. The questions were answered on a five-point scale. For differences in significance, tabular analysis was used using SPSS (Social Sciences Statistics Package) software to find correlations between different variables.

RESULTS:

The study involved 450 patients. The first two questions in the questionnaire attempted to assess the patient's overall satisfaction and comfort when wearing a denture; the next seven questions were created to assess important aspects of satisfaction, and the last three questions attempted to examine some of the psychological consequences of prosthetic activity. Table 1 shows the distribution of responses with alternative answers and the percentage distribution of responses according to the variables covered in this study. Attitude to prostheses showed that 394 (87.5%) patients thought it was a general denture, and suspected that 301 (66.8%) experienced comfortable well-being and coped well with prostheses. When testing the functional appearance of the prosthesis, 380 (84.4%) thought it would have a permanent denture and 411 (91.3%) suspected it would have a permanent denture. Saying 114 (25.3%) thought that 412 (91.5%) eats well and loses taste due to 22 (4.8%) prostheses. Only 18 (4%) thought that he would look older and would not improve the appearance of dentures, 45 (10%) suspected that he felt pain when wearing a denture. While 252 (56%) feel prosthetics as part of themselves, 439 (87.5%) thought they would improve communication with other people

and recommend treatment for the same number of friends. Table 1

TABLE 1: SHOW RESULTS OF PATIENT ATTITUDE AND CORRELATION TO SATISFACTION

Questions	Attitude				CorrelationP*
	Yes	%	No	%	
General Satisfaction	394	87.5	56	12.4	0.868
Comfortable	301	66.8	149	33.1	0.866
Retention	380	84.4	70	15.5	0.892
Stability	411	91.3	39	8.6	0.808
Speech	336	74.6	114	25.4	0.871
Chewing	412	91.5	38	8.5	0.808
Taste	438	97.3	22	2.7	0.843
Appearance	432	96	18	4	0.866
Pain	405	90	45	10	0.877
Foreign Body	252	56	198	44	0.593
Communication with People	439	97.5	11	2.5	0.641
Recommendation	430	95.5	20	4.5	0.832

*= correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

After installing the new prosthesis for three months, 302 (67.1%) patients were satisfied with the new prosthesis and 295 (65.5%) felt comfortable wearing it. Three hundred eighty-eight (86.2%) accepted the durability of their prostheses as retainers according to 228 (49.8%) and said they were stable in speech, diet and flavors worn in prosthetics. 363 (80.6%), 262 (58.2%), 282 (62.6%) were satisfied with these positions, and 295 (65.5%) were satisfied with their appearance. The results regarding the psychological acceptance of treatment showed that 322 (71.5%) considered themselves prosthetic as part of them, 286 (62.6%) considered it easy to communicate with other people, 326 (72.4%) considered that they would recommend treatment to others (Table 2).

TABLE 2: SHOW RESULTS OF PATIENT SATISFACTION

Questions	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		I don't know (not sure)		Agree		Strongly agree	
	Disagree	%	Disagree	%	I don't know (not sure)	%	Agree	%	Strongly agree	%
General Satisfaction	55	12.22%	63	14.00%	30	6.67%	133	29.56%	169	37.56%
Retention	17	3.78%	35	7.78%	10	2.22%	256	56.89%	132	29.33%
Stability	67	14.89%	69	15.33%	86	19.11%	121	26.89%	107	23.78%
Speak	17	3.78%	62	13.78%	8	1.78%	298	66.22%	65	14.44%
Chewing	78	17.33%	77	17.11%	33	7.33%	167	37.11%	95	21.11%
Taste	52	11.56%	89	19.78%	27	6.00%	199	44.22%	83	18.44%
Comfortable	53	11.78%	76	16.89%	26	5.78%	242	53.78%	53	11.78%
Appearance	15	3.33%	62	13.78%	78	17.33%	197	43.78%	98	21.78%
Pain	45	10.00%	42	9.33%	25	5.56%	196	43.56%	142	31.56%
Foreign Body	135	30.00%	187	41.56%	88	19.56%	22	4.89%	18	4.00%
Communication with People	121	26.89%	165	36.67%	113	25.11%	39	8.67%	12	2.67%
Recommendation	12	2.67%	98	21.78%	14	3.11%	205	45.56%	121	26.89%

DISCUSSION:

Because patient satisfaction is a prerequisite for successful full denture treatment when assessing their own dentures, the sample size (450 patients) participating in this study can be monitored and convinced to see its effect. Although the patients in this study were provide free care to their patients,

only people with good physical and mental illnesses (normal patients) were selected⁹⁻¹⁰. In addition, because this study also suggests that patients can distinguish between different satisfaction variables, selected questions are easy to apply and can be assessed by any normal person; the importance of continuous response to patients was emphasized. In

addition, the attitude of the patient to new prostheses and the satisfaction that patients appreciate were noted by a senior specialist who oversaw the construction of the prostheses.

Because this study aimed to determine the relationship between patient expectations and satisfaction and specific aspects of prostheses, patients were asked to express their overall satisfaction expectations before starting treatment¹¹⁻¹². Both variables (overall satisfaction and comfort) are the most important variables that can explain satisfaction with the functional aspects of the prosthesis, the results of this study are consistent with the findings of previous studies and documents examining the patient's attitude and satisfaction¹³. Towards your dentures. When patients were asked to express their expectations for the functional efficiency of future prostheses and to compare the results with the results obtained three months after use, a strong relationship between various variables, the presence of overall satisfaction, and durable, aesthetic and aesthetically acceptable dentures was also found. The last 3 questions concerned some psychological aspects. All patients had generally positive reviews about their future prosthesis compatible with the newly installed prosthesis after three months of use, other studies also showed similar results¹⁴.

It has been shown that there is a strong relationship between pre-placement measurements and patient satisfaction after 3 months of use. This result was supported by other studies that showed such a strong relationship; while other studies have shown a moderately positive relationship, no significant relationship was found among others. Langer et al. He noted that the success and acceptance of all prostheses by the patient depends on the interaction of various functional, psychological and constructive factors consistent with this study. In addition, Van Waas stated that patients' attitudes towards prostheses may play an important role in the future of dentures because they respond positively to people who think more often. Jonkman et al. He stated that the approach to the use of dental prostheses is a forward-looking tool for assessing satisfaction with the use of full dentures¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

A good positive correlation was found between patient attitude before receiving the denture and satisfaction with the new denture. This study supports other studies which reported that attitude of the patient toward denture is a prospective tool to predict patient dissatisfaction with new denture.

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